

LCA Sustainability assessments in SSbD

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Abstract

Sustainability assessments in SSbD are outlined to consist of assessments regarding Environmental, Economic and Social aspects of the innovation under investigation. Sometimes this is formalized to consist of (Environmental) Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Costing (LCC) and Social Life Cycle Assessment, (S-LCA). The current session will focus on the environmental assessment (LCA) but will also briefly introduce the economic and social aspects. LCA is a methodology aimed at evaluating the potential environmental impacts of products, processes, and services across their full life cycle, where processes are connected by mass or energy flows. Standardized in the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO) 14040 standards series it distinguishes four phases: i) Goal and scope definition, ii) creation of the life cycle inventory (LCI), iii) life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) and iv) interpretation. In SSbD, a specific challenge for the LCA practitioner, which also extends to the overall sustainability assessment, is the need to do the assessment at as low TRL as possible, when synthesis routes and processes are only known in lab scale. The approach applied in LCA is referred to as prospective LCA, and is typically useful in an intermediate TRL. For really low TRL levels, qualitative approaches such as discussion with experts or questionnaire based approaches. At higher TRLs, more descriptive approaches can be applied. In the session, an overview of the different LCA approaches along the TRL sequence will be provided.